

gasocrine: relating to biological and non-biological processes that release gases

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I have recently proposed a new term, "gasocrine signaling", to unify cellular signaling based on gas-sensing gasoreceptor proteins or yet-to-be-identified gas-sensing riboceptors (1,2). However, the definition of **gasocrine** has not been explicitly stated in the scientific literature. I propose the definition of gasocrine as: relating to biological and non-biological processes that release gases.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

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